

INTEGRATION OF SOLAR- POWERED DYNAMIC VOLTAGE RESTORERS FOR IMPROVED POWER QUALITY IN DISTRIBUTED SYSTEMS.

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the Integration of solar-powered dynamic voltage restorer in a distribution system in order to enhance power quality in Finima, Bonny Island power distribution system, which has been characterized with voltage sags and voltage swells, thereby, creating power quality issues. To mitigate these power quality problems, solar powered DVR with Artificial Neural Network Controller (ANN) is installed in the network and simulated using MATLAB/Simulink 2018 application software tool. The simulation results obtained from the existing network shows that nine (9) bus voltage violates nominal voltage limit (0.95-1.0Pu). But, when solar powered DVR with artificial neural network controller was installed in the network, all bus voltages lies within the nominal voltage limit(0.95-1.0pu) as stipulated by IEEE, also, it compensate voltage sags during disturbance on the distribution system in a short time (less than 20ms) and prevent tripping or loss of sensitive loads. It also reduces the Total Harmonics Distortion (THD) less than 5%.

Keywords: Dynamic Voltage Restorer, Artificial Neural Network, IEEE, MATLAB/Simulink, Voltage Sag, Sensitive Load, Total Harmonic Distortion

INTRODUCTION

In modern economies, demand for access to stable, reliable and quality power supply cannot be overemphasized, since socio economic development, industrialization and technological development anchors on electricity availability [1]. Power quality problems such as; voltage sags or swells, as well as distortions due to transients, frequency and harmonics are major challenges facing power supply distribution systems nowadays, which may results to degradation of power supply to the consumers, economic loss to both the consumers and the utility on the long run[2][3]. Power quality problems are caused by faults in the power transmission or distribution network, faults in consumer's installation, starting of large motors etc. But due to rapid advancement in electronics devices, all categories of consumers (Industrial, commercial and residential) connected equipment that are made up of electronic components, which are extremely sensitive to changes like voltage sags/swells and harmonics interference to the power system (4).

The equipment normally connected to the distribution system includes: variable speed drives (VSD), rectifiers and power electronic devices (computers, television, printers, photocopiers, telecoms systems, microwave etc),

which are non- linear in nature. These non- linear equipment generate harmonics that compounded power quality issues affecting distribution system and loads connected to it [5]. The problems associated with power quality in distribution system especially in developing countries like Nigeria, has become a reoccurring phenomenon, due to mismatch between available units of energy generated and units demanded as a results of population increase.

In order to mitigate or ameliorate power quality disturbances in distribution system, there are two known strategies to be applied, either to ensure that the process equipment is less responsive to disturbances, allowing it to ride-through the disturbances, or installing a custom power device such as: Dynamic voltage restorer (DVR) to suppress or neutralize the disturbances at the load end of the distribution system. DVR is one of most known effective dynamic and efficient custom power electronic device used to inject voltage in series with distribution feeder in order to compensate for voltage sag/swell [6]. This research provides an insight on the introduction of DVR, which is a series voltage compensation power electronic device for mitigation of power quality problems in a typical distribution system

Statement of the Problem

The Bonny Island power distribution system is characterized by high availability of electricity supplied, but the community suffers by not getting reliable and quality power supply due to the activities of multinationals companies in the Island, who brought all sort of electronics devices to power system thereby creating inherent power quality problems such as voltage sag or swells and harmonic distortion. This has created lots of negative impact on the economy and business activities on the island, as equipment connected to the distribution system by consumers are getting damaged, resulting to economic loss. The power quality problem is manifested in voltage or frequency deviations that result in failure or mal-operation of customer equipment [7].

Therefore, the shortfall in power quality need to be addressed with the requisite planning and adoption of approach that would guarantee safe and reliable power system. This research seeks to inject solar powered dynamic voltage restorer in Bonny Island distribution system for power quality enhancement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dynamic Voltage Restorer

A Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR) is a solid-state inverter used for injection of voltage in series with a power distributed system. DVR is recognized as one of the most effective and efficient modern custom power device used in power distribution networks to inject voltage into distribution feeder in order to compensate for voltage sag/swell [8]. DVR is a series compensation device, which protects sensitive electric load from power quality problems such as voltage sags, swells, unbalance and distortion through power electronic controllers that use voltage source converters (VSC).

Basic Composition and Principle of DVR Operation

A DVR is a solid-state power electronics switching device consisting of either GTO, MOSFET or IGBT, a capacitor depository as a power storage device and inoculation transformer [9]. It is connected in series between a distribution system and a load. The DC side of DVR is connected to an energy source or an energy storage

device, while its AC side is connected to the distribution feeder by a three-phase interfacing injection transformer as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conventional Circuit Configuration of DVR [10]

The DVR is capable to generate or absorb reactive power but the active power injection of the device must be provided by an external energy storage system. The response time of DVR is very short and is limited by the power electronics devices. The basic operation principle of dynamic voltage restorer is to inject a voltage of required magnitude and frequency, so that it can restore the load side voltage to the desired amplitude and waveform even when the source voltage is unbalanced or distorted. Generally, it employs a gate turn off thyristor (GTO) solid state power electronic switches in a pulse width modulated (PWM) inverter structure[11]. A DC to AC inverter regulates the voltage by sinusoidal PWM technique. At normal operating condition, the DVR inject only a small voltage to compensate for the voltage drop of the injection transformer and device losses. However, when voltage sag occurs in the distribution system, the DVR controls stem calculates and synthesizes the voltage required to preserve output voltage to the load by injecting a controlled voltage with a certain magnitude and phase angle into the distribution system then to the critical load [12].

Control Strategies of DVR

As regards power quality improvement in the distribution system using DVR, there are numerous techniques of control strategies to implement. Most of the identified DVR systems are equipped with a control system that is configured to mitigate voltage sags/swells. Other DVR application includes harmonic control, power flow control, reactive power compensation as well as limited responses to power quality problems [13].

Maintaining constant voltage magnitude at the point where a sensitive load is connected under system disturbances is the main function of the control scheme. The control system only measures the r.m.s. voltage at

the load point i.e. no reactive power measurements are required. The control scheme of DVR involves detection of voltage sags and the required algorithms which can work in real time [14]

The inverter has two types of control methods namely: Linear control and non-linear control. Linear control method of DVR control is the linear and the ones commonly employed are: feed forward control, feedback control and composite control. The combination of feedback control with feed forward control can improve the system dynamic response rate, shortening the time of compensation significantly [15]. The employment of semi-conductor switches in the voltage stability improvement has made DVR to be categorized as non-linear device, once the system became unstable, the linear models developed cannot efficiently control the target voltage, due to their limitation, hence the need for non-linear control. Examples of these methods are: Artificial Neural Network (ANN) control, Fuzzy Control and Space Vector PWM (SVPWM) Control

In the proposed paper by [16], they carried out a study on the use of compensation dynamic voltage restorer (DVR) to damped voltage sag, the DVR uses a three-phase voltage source inverter (VSI) with voltage loop control (PI). Park transformation was used to detect the voltage drop system, and it was applied in the voltage regulator as a control system function that detects the voltage amplitude at the sensitive load continuously. The result of simulation in system distribution with an active load 280 kVA and 50 kVAR reactive, before a voltage compensation system was 0.67 pu and after voltage compensation system becomes 0.99 pu on nominal voltage of 380V. They concluded that the performance of DVR is reliable because it is able to compensate quickly to changes in the value of the voltage

In the proposed study by [10], they carried out a study power quality improvement using dynamic voltage restorer. Voltage was injected into a distribution line to maintain the voltage profile and assures constant load voltage. The simulations were conducted in MATLAB/Simulink to show the DVR-based proposed strategy's effectiveness to smooth the distorted voltage due to harmonics. A power system model with a programmable power source is used to include 3rd and 5th harmonics. The systems' response for load voltage is evaluated for with and without DVR scenario. The proposed DVR based strategy has effectively managed the voltage distortion, and a smooth compensated load voltage was achieved. The load voltage THD percentage was approximately 18% and 23% with insertion 3rd and 5th harmonics in the supply voltage, respectively. The inclusion of the proposed DVR has reduced THD around less than 4% in both cases.

[17], in their study, they developed a DVR based on an artificial neural network (ANN) controller. The activation function employed was Train LM for the input hidden layers, and pure linear for the output layer, with the Levenberg Marquardt back propagation (LMBP) serving as the training algorithm. The designed model was then tested to tackle voltage-related power quality problems in the distribution network of Jamal Din Wala (JDW) sugar mills. The comprehensive model featured a three-phase voltage source inverter, a scheme utilizing rotating reference frame theory, and sine pulse width modulation (SPWM) for voltage sag and swell sensing along with insulated gate

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials

The materials used in this study include:

- i. Single line diagram of existing 11kV Finima, Bonny Island Distribution Network
- ii. Line data of the study case distribution network
- iii. Load data of the study case distribution network
- iv. DVR with twisting sliding mode controller tool
- v. MATLAB/Simulink 2018 Application Software

Method Used

The research method employed in this study is simulation, dynamic voltage restorer with solar powered storage unit and artificial neural network (ANN) controller was used to monitor the Finima, Bonny Island distribution network voltage to detect any disturbances and control the injection of voltage into the distribution system to mitigate voltage disturbances and restore power quality. The modelling and implementation was done in MATLAB/Simulink tool.

System Under investigation

The Finima distribution Feeder (R4) in Bonny Island is chosen for this study because it has low voltage (voltage sag) issues when compared to other feeders due to transmission losses and overload issues. It also has many industrial and commercial customers connected to it. Figure 2 shows the single line diagram of Finima, Bonny Island 11kV Power Distribution Network, it consists of sixteen (16) 11/0.415kV distribution transformer substations.

Figure 2: Finima, Bonny Island 11kV Power Distribution Network

Table 1 shows the parameters of the DVR used in this study. Table 2 and 3, show the load profile and line data of existing Finima, Bonny 11kV distribution network respectively.

Table I: DVR Parameters

DVR	
Rated Capacity	750 KVA
Maximum Injection Capacity- three phase	$\leq 75\%$
Maximum Voltage Injection (Single phase)	180V
Injection Transformer	
Rated Capacity	250 KVA
Nominal Power	3 x 250KVA
Primary Winding Voltage	100V
Secondary Winding Voltage	180V
Inverter	
Inverter Capacity	3 x 250 KVA
Semiconductor Voltage	140, 0.4 V
DC Battery	
Voltage(dc)	430V
Data of Semi-conductor Devices	
Ideal switch voltage (peak)	140
Diode Voltage (peak)	140
Forward Voltage	0.4

Table 2: Load Data R4 Feeder of Bonny Distribution System at 0.8 PF

S/No	BUS	Capacity (KVA)	Voltage Rating (KV)	I _R (A)	I _Y (A)	I _B (A)	I _N (A)	Voltage (V)
1	Bakery	500	33/0.415	616	638	777	-	381.9
2	NLNG Roundabout	300	33/0.415	439.8	459	423	-	379
3	Long House	500	11/0.415	441	399	380	-	386
4	Police Station	500	11/0.415	705	492	628	-	395
5	Powerhouse	500	11/0.415	436	654	755	-	395

6	Zone 1	500	11/0.415	699	597	515	-	362
7	One Man Bus-stop	500	11/0.415	710	612	582	-	370
8	CAC	500	11/0.415	594	555	667	-	374
9	Zone 4	500	11/0.415	839.6	701	640	-	364
10	Zone 5	500	11/0.415	446	421	480	-	363
11	Princess Hotel	200	33/0.415	99	83	98	-	371
12	Atlantic Hotel	500	33/0.415	183	197	199	-	379
13	Zone 6 - Front	500	11/0.415	431	430	516	-	376
14	Zone 6 - Back	500	11/0.415	298	302	279	-	365
15	Meger Star	300	33/0.415	13	11	9	-	379
16	Redeem	500	11/0.415	636	630	603	-	364

Source: Bonny Utility Company (BUC)

Table 3: Line Data R4 Feeder of Bonny Distribution System

S/No	From Bus	To Bus	Impedance (Z)
1	Bakery	NLNG Roundabout	0.017 + j0.043
2	NLNG Roundabout	Long House	0.027 + j0.035
3	Long House	Police Station	0.035 + j0.047
4	Police Station	Powerhouse	0.041 + j0.038
5	Powerhouse	Zone 1	0.030 + j0.021
6	Zone 1	One Man Bus-stop	0.020 + j0.036
7	One Man Bus-stop	CAC	0.025 + j0.039
8	CAC	Zone 4	0.053 + j0.061
9	Zone 4	Zone 5	0.027 + j0.058

10	Zone 5	Princess Hotel	$0.033 + j0.012$
11	Princess Hotel	Atlantic Hotel	$0.066 + j0.047$
12	Atlantic Hotel	Zone 6 - Front	$0.083 + j0.035$
13	Zone 6 - Front	Zone 6 - Back	$0.015 + j0.041$
14	Zone 6 - Back	Mega Star	$0.050 + j0.43$
15	Mega Star	Redeem	$0.025 + j0.060$
16	Redeem	end	$5j 0.4056$

Source: Bonny Utility Company (BUC).

Modelling of Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR)

The DVR system is made up of a PV powered storage unit, DC link, voltage source PWM inverter, L-C filter, injection transformer and ANN based controller. Figure 3 shows the block diagram of power and control circuits of the dynamic voltage restorer used for this study. It is modelled by constructing its individual components using MATLAB/Simulink.

The power circuit of the modelled DVR comprises 3-phase 2-level PWM voltage source inverter with a group of battery source which are recharged using photovoltaic system. In this system, the control system is not required to regulate the dc link voltage. The primary side of the transformers is connected to the distribution network in series and then the secondary sides are connected to the VSI in star configuration to eliminate zero-sequence voltage in an unbalanced voltage condition.

The inverter transforms the DC voltage supplied by the batteries to AC voltage. The AC voltage is then injected via the series transformer to the network. The VSI controls the IGBT in a Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) structure then reconvert it to AC voltage in an event of power quality disturbances. The AC output of the converter is filtered using a passive L-C filter to produce a pure voltage waveform that is injected into the power system through the coupling transformer connected in series with the distribution system. The L-C filter removes the switching harmonic components from the compensation voltage. In case, it is placed at the secondary side of the transformer (output side of VSI) in order to prevent the higher order harmonics from passing through the transformer and thereby, reducing the voltage stress on the transformer. This, in turn, reduces size of the injection transformer required for the compensation.

Figure 3: Block Diagram of DVR Modelling

Characteristics Equations

Source voltage

The source voltage is given by

$$V_s = v_{1n}(\sin(\omega t + \theta_{1n})) + v_{1p}(\sin(\omega t + \theta_{1p})) + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} v_k(k\omega t + \theta_k) \tag{1}$$

Where

v_{1n} : fundamental frequency of component of negative sequence

v_{1p} : fundamental frequency of component of positive sequence.

v_k : harmonic component

$\theta_{1n}, \theta_{1p}, \theta_k$: phase angle of voltages

DC Link Voltage

The dc voltage is giving by

$$V_{dc} = \frac{2\sqrt{2} V_{LL}}{\sqrt{3}} \tag{2}$$

Where:

V_{dc} : dc bus voltage

V_{LL} : ac line voltage

Modulation Index

The modulation index is given by

$$k = \frac{\sqrt{2}V_0}{V_{dc}} \quad (3)$$

Where

V_0 is nominal load voltage

V_{dc} is the dc link voltage

Filter Factor

The filter factor is given by

$$FF = \left(\frac{k^2 - 3.75k^2 + 4.07k^5 - 1.25k^6}{1440} \right)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

Where:

K is modulation factor

Inductance L

The inductance is given by

$$L = \frac{V_0}{I_0 f_s} \left(FF \frac{V_{dc}}{V_h} \left(1 + 4\pi^2 \frac{f_r^2}{f_s^2} FF \frac{V_{dc}}{V_h} \right) \right)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

Where:

V_h : the total harmonic of the load voltage

f_r : fundamental frequency

f_s : switching frequency

I_0 : the load current

Capacitor C

The capacitance is given by

$$C = FF \frac{V_{dc}}{L f_s^2 V_h} \quad (6)$$

Where

V_{dc} : the dc link voltage

FF : the filter factor

L : the inductance

f_s : switching frequency

V_h : the total harmonic of the load voltage

DVR Control Scheme Algorithm

These are the steps of the DVR control scheme algorithm:

Step 1: Transform the load currents from a-b-c frame to α - β frame using Clark-Park's transformation.

$$\begin{pmatrix} i_\alpha \\ i_\beta \\ i_0 \end{pmatrix} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i_{La} \\ i_{Lb} \\ i_{Lc} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Step 2: Process the voltage signal to generate $\sin\theta$ and $\cos\theta$ signal using PLL then transform the load currents from α - β frame to d-q. SRF isolator extracts the dc component using low-pass filters (LPFs).

$$\begin{pmatrix} i_d \\ i_q \\ i_0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\theta & \sin\theta & 0 \\ -\sin\theta & \cos\theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i_\alpha \\ i_\beta \\ i_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Step 3: Using inverse Clark-Park's transformation, the dc component of the load current in d-q frame is transformed back to three phase reference currents in a-b-c frame which is further fed to the PWM signal generator to generate switching signals for the DVR

$$\begin{pmatrix} i_{La} \\ i_{Lb} \\ i_{Lc} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\theta & -\sin\theta & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \cos\left(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) & -\sin\left(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \cos\left(\theta - \frac{4\pi}{3}\right) & -\sin\left(\theta - \frac{4\pi}{3}\right) & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i_d \\ i_q \\ i_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Figure 4 and 5, show Finima distribution network diagram modelled in Matlab/ Simulink environment without and with the DVR installed respectively.

Figure 4: Simulink Model of Bonny Distribution System without DVR

Figure 5: Simulink Model of Bonny Distribution System with DVR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Discussion of Voltage Stability With and Without DVR

The study case distribution network was simulated in Matlab/Simulink environment under two (2) scenarios to assess the effectiveness of the proposed DVR system in improving power quality. In the first scenario, the existing network was simulated without the installation of DVR. The simulation results shows that the operating voltage values (pu) of nine (9) substations did not meet the nominal voltage limits of 0.95 – 1.0 pu as declared by IEEE without the installation of the DVR. The results is as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Voltage Profile without DVR

S/No	BUS	Voltage Levels (kV)	Nominal Voltage (V)	Operating Voltage (V)	Operating Voltage (pu)
1	Bakery	33/0.415	400	381.9	0.95
2	NLNG Roundabout	33/0.415	400	379	0.95
3	Long House	11/0.415	400	386	0.97
4	Police Station	11/0.415	400	395	0.99
5	Powerhouse	11/0.415	400	395	0.99
6	Zone 1	11/0.415	400	362	0.91
7	One Man Bus-stop	11/0.415	400	370	0.93
8	CAC	11/0.415	400	374	0.94
9	Zone 4	11/0.415	400	364	0.91
10	Zone 5	11/0.415	400	363	0.91
11	Princess Hotel	33/0.415	400	371	0.93
12	Atlantic Hotel	33/0.415	400	379	0.95
13	Zone 6 - Front	11/0.415	400	376	0.94
14	Zone 6 - Back	11/0.415	400	365	0.91
15	Meger Star	33/0.415	400	379	0.95
16	Redeem	11/0.415	400	364	0.91

In the second scenario, a modelled solar powered DVR with ANN controller was then installed in the study case distribution network and simulated. The simulation results show improved operating voltage values obtained at affected buses after insertion of the DVR in the network. The operating voltages are all within the acceptable nominal limits (0.95 – 1.0pu). This implies that that the proposed DVR adequately mitigated the voltage sags issues and improved the voltage profile of the network under investigation. The results is as shown in Table 5.

Table 4: Voltage Profile with DVR

S/No	BUS	Voltage Levels (kV)	Nominal Voltage (V)	Operating Voltage (V)	Operating Voltage (pu)
1	Bakery	33/0.415	400	381.9	0.95
2	NLNG Roundabout	33/0.415	400	389	0.97
3	Long House	11/0.415	400	386	0.97
4	Police Station	11/0.415	400	395	0.99
5	Powerhouse	11/0.415	400	395	0.99
6	Zone 1	11/0.415	400	382	0.96
7	One Man Bus-stop	11/0.415	400	380	0.95
8	CAC	11/0.415	400	384	0.96
9	Zone 4	11/0.415	400	384	0.96
10	Zone 5	11/0.415	400	393	0.98
11	Princess Hotel	33/0.415	400	391	0.98
12	Atlantic Hotel	33/0.415	400	389	0.97
13	Zone 6 - Front	11/0.415	400	386	0.97
14	Zone 6 - Back	11/0.415	400	385	0.96
15	Meger Star	33/0.415	400	379	0.95
16	Redeem	11/0.415	400	394	0.99

• **Voltage Compensation under Different Fault Scenarios**

With the view to assess the compensation ability of the modelled DVR under different fault scenarios, the distribution network was simulated without and with the DVR for three phase to ground fault, double line to ground fault and single line to ground fault.

• **Three Phase-to-Ground Fault**

When a three phase to ground fault was initiated in study case distribution network with the modelled DVR system at Bus TS-3 for a duration of 0.2 seconds (between 0.6 – 0.8 secs), voltage sag was observed in the voltage waveform as shown in Figure 6. The DVR through the ANN controller senses the disturbance and then rapidly responded by injecting a compensating voltage to restore the pre fault load voltage. The DVR injects compensation voltage in the required magnitude and phase angle for recovery of the line operating voltage. Also, the total harmonic distortion (THD) was reduced from 12.53 recorded before the compensation to 1.84 after the compensation. This means that the proposed system is able to mitigate the voltage sag caused by the three phase-to-ground fault. It is able to restore and maintain the line voltage and THD within the acceptable nominal values.

Figure 6: Plot of Three Phase to Ground Fault Voltage Disturbance Waveform

• **Double Phase to Ground Fault**

When a double phase to ground fault was initiated in the distribution system, the simulation results indicates an unbalanced voltage sag on the voltage waveform (blue and yellow phases collapsed). The ANN modelled DVR similarly detected the condition and injected the required compensation voltage for recovery of the affected phases voltages as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Plot of Double Phase to Ground Fault Voltage Disturbance Waveform

- **Single Phase to Ground Fault**

When a single line to ground fault was initiated in the network, the distribution network experienced unbalance voltage sag on one phase (red phase). At that moment, the affected phase voltage magnitude and phase angle were quickly compensated by the DVR system. This is as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Plot of Single Phase to Ground Fault Voltage Disturbance Waveform

CONCLUSION

This study focused on the penetration of solar powered dynamic voltage restorer (DVR) with an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) controller for power quality improvement, using Finima, Bonny Island 11kV power distribution network as case study because, the distribution system is characterized by voltage disturbances due to losses and excessive loading. Voltage sags or swells is one of the critical issues affecting power quality in the power distribution network. Voltage sag occurs due to overloading, faults in the system, and side effects of connecting electronic equipment on the distribution system. Therefore, mitigating this problems in power distribution system is crucial for operating a reliable and stable power system. The photovoltaic system was employed to enhance recharging of the battery storage system which enables the DVR to mitigate voltage disturbances such as voltage sag for a prolonged period. The study was carried out using data obtained from Bonny Utility Company (BUC)

The study case distribution network was modeled in MATLAB/Simulink 2018 application software. The result obtained shows that the proposed approach and method mitigated three-phase sags/swell up to 50% of the nominal voltage. It was observed that the installation of DVR in the distribution network successfully improved the operating voltages to acceptable limits and mitigate the power quality issues to consumers. It also help to significantly reduce the Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) level in the network.

REFERENCES

- Nneze, A.F., Ezeodili, W. & Nze, U.L. (2024). Effect of power supply on the socio-economic development of South East, Nigeria. *Journal of Policy and Development Studies (JPDS)* 16(2), 13-34.
- Deshmukh, S.M., Gawande, S. P. & Dewani, B. (2013). A review of power quality problems –voltage sags for different faults. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Technology*, 2(5), 392-397.
- Johnson, D.O. & Hassan, K.A. (2016). Issues of power quality in electrical systems substation. *Journal of Energy and Power Engineering*, 5(4), 148-154
- Patil, R. M., Nagaraj, M. S. & Venkataramu, P. S. (2015). Harmonic problems in the switching devices with respect to electrical power quality point of view. *International Journal of Science, Technology & Management*, 04(03), 17-34
- Rustemli, S., Satici, A., Sahin, G. & Sark, W. V. (2023). Investigation of harmonics analysis power system due to non-linear loads on electrical energy quality results. *Energy Reports*, 10(1), 4704-4732
- El- Gammal, M., Abou-Ghazala, A.Y. & El-Shennawy, T. (2011). Dynamic voltage restorer (DVR) for voltage sag mitigation. *International Journal on Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 3(1), 1-11
- Ananth, D. V. N., Hannon, N., Mohammed- Yunus, M.S., Jamaludin, M.H., Charavarthy, S.V.V.S. & Chowdary, P.S. R. (2023). Real- time power quality measurement audit of government building – A case study in compliance with IEEE 1159. *ACTA IMEKO*, 12(1), 1-9.
- Tumus, S., Harika, A., Jayanthu, S. & Lakshmi, J. (2019). Improvement of power quality using DVR by different control techniques. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, 8(3), 736-369
- Moghassemi, A. & Padmanaban, S. (2020). Dynamic voltage restorer (DVR) : A comprehensive review of topologies, power converters, control methods and modified configurations. *Energies*, 13(16).1-38.
- Abass, N., Dilshad, S., Khalid, A., Saleem, S. & Khan, N. (2022). Power quality improvement using dynamic voltage restorer. *IEEE Access*, 8 (1), 1- 15
- Kumar, P. (2014). Enhancement of power quality by an application of DVR. *Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IOSR-IEEE)*, 2(2014), 31 – 36.

- Kumar, Singh, G & Jindal, V. (2015). Voltage correction methods in distribution system using DVR. *International Journal of Research Studies in Science, Engineering and Technology* ,2(6), 52-63
- Kumar, A. & Kumar, D. (2022). Mitigation of power quality problems and harmonics compensation using capacitor supported dynamic voltage restorer (DVR). *Journal of Electrical Engineering*, 17(2), 1-12
- Khoshkbar-Sadigh, A. & Smedley, K.M. (2016). Fast and precise voltage sag detection method for dynamic voltage restorer (DVR) application. *Electric Power System Research*, 130(1), 192 – 207
- Omar, R., Rahim, N.A. & Sulaiman, M. (2011) Dynamic voltage restorer application for power quality improvement in electrical distribution system: An overview. *Journal of Basic and Applied Science*, 5(12), 1-12.
- Martiningsih, W., Prakoso, U. Y. & Herudin, A. (2018). Power quality improvement using dynamic voltage restorer in distribution system P.T DSS power plant. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 218 (01003), 1- 9
- Siddique, A., Mujahid, A., Aslam, W., Sajid, M. & Arteen, Z.A. (2023). Improvements in voltage profile of JDW sugar mills Jawar distribution feeder RYK Pakistan using ANN based dynamic voltage restorer. *Journal Europeen des Systemes Automalises*, 57 (1), 1- 8